

SciComm Readiness Tool For Institutions

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In recent years, there has been a growing expectation for universities and research institutions in India to enhance their communication strategies, ensuring effective and timely engagement with a diverse range of non-science and non-expert audiences. This imperative arises for a multitude of reasons, such as accountability to the taxpayer, attracting talent and funding, necessitating a proactive approach to making research and science accessible to diverse audiences, and enhancing the public's participation in science. For institutions to be able to fulfil these diverse needs in an effective and timely manner, they must establish and uphold a robust framework for Science Communication (SciComm) and Public Engagement (PE). However, Indian scientific institutions are at various stages of developing their commitment and capacity for SciComm/PE.

This **SciComm Readiness Tool** has been designed to help institutions assess their current commitment and capacity for SciComm/PE. The tool also indicates measures the institutions can take to improve their ability in SciComm/PE in line with the growing demands. Funders can also use the tool to review an institution's commitment and ability to make its research accessible and engage with the public on scientific matters.

The tool should be discussed and completed by various stakeholders in the institution, including leadership, administration, SciComm/PE staff (if available), faculty, and students, so that it is an unbiased representation of the institute's SciComm capabilities and commitment. Refer to the glossary in case you are unclear about any of the terms mentioned in the tool. Based on the total number of statements that stand true for your institution under each category, you should be able to self-evaluate your institute as low, moderate, or high on SciComm readiness. For institutions to fulfil the imperatives assigned to them, they should aspire to achieve a 'High SciComm Readiness' level.

We envision this evaluation system with indicators to be used as a tool by institutions to inform and support their development of SciComm/PE structures and practices.

Note:

1) The term SciComm/PE is used in this document to describe the process of communicating and engaging with non-scientific or non-expert audiences about scientific research and science more broadly towards generating mutual benefit.

2) This is not a comprehensive tool and will be updated periodically to incorporate the latest trends, user feedback, and evolving needs within the dynamic landscape of science and research communication.

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Write to sarahhyderiqbal@gmail.com to provide feedback and suggestions for this tool.

SciComm Readiness Tool For Institutions

Parameters	Low SciComm readiness	Moderate SciComm readiness	High SciComm readiness
Mission	<input type="checkbox"/> There is no mention of SciComm/PE in the institutional vision, mission, and strategy. <input type="checkbox"/> SciComm/PE is not an institutional priority.	<input type="checkbox"/> There is some mention of SciComm/PE in the institutional vision, mission, and strategy. <input type="checkbox"/> SciComm/PE is considered an institutional priority.	<input type="checkbox"/> There is a clear mention of SciComm/PE in the institutional vision, mission, and strategy. <input type="checkbox"/> SciComm/PE is considered an institutional priority. <input type="checkbox"/> The institution invests in developing a SciComm/PE strategy for a defined period.
Leadership	<input type="checkbox"/> None of the influential leaders in the institution serve as champions for SciComm/PE.	<input type="checkbox"/> Some of the institution's senior team members act as informal champions for SciComm/PE.	<input type="checkbox"/> The Director/VC acts as a champion for public engagement and a senior leader takes formal responsibility. <input type="checkbox"/> All senior staff have an understanding of the importance and value of SciComm/PE to the institution's agenda.
People	<input type="checkbox"/> There is no dedicated full-time staff for SciComm/PE. <input type="checkbox"/> Research or administrative staff at the institution serves the SciComm/PE function in a part-time capacity.	<input type="checkbox"/> Dedicated full-time staff for SciComm/PE. <input type="checkbox"/> ~70% of their work is related to SciComm/PE-related activities. <input type="checkbox"/> Somewhat clear job description for SciComm/PE roles, with a few areas of ambiguity.	<input type="checkbox"/> Dedicated SciComm/PE Office/Department <input type="checkbox"/> Dedicated staff for each of the distinct SciComm functions such as research communication, social media, website, public engagement, and outreach. <input type="checkbox"/> >90% of their work is related to SciComm/PE <input type="checkbox"/> Well-defined job descriptions for SciComm/PE staff
Processes	<input type="checkbox"/> No governance structures for SciComm/PE function (for example, hiring policies, SOPs, etc.)	<input type="checkbox"/> Basic governance structures for the SciComm/PE function.	<input type="checkbox"/> Clear and tailored governance structures that effectively support SciComm/PE staff and activities.

	<input type="checkbox"/> No organisational strategy for the SciComm/PE	<input type="checkbox"/> Basic strategy for the SciComm/PE activities.	<input type="checkbox"/> Clear institutional strategy for SciComm/PE with intended outcomes, timelines, evaluation plan, resources, etc. <input type="checkbox"/> Well-defined SOPs for all standard SciComm/PE practices/activities.
Infrastructure	<input type="checkbox"/> No infrastructure dedicated to SciComm/PE <input type="checkbox"/> Lack of specialised tools/platforms for creating and disseminating SciComm/PE resources. <input type="checkbox"/> No physical/digital spaces for hosting SciComm/PE events/activities.	<input type="checkbox"/> Moderate infrastructure to support SciComm/PE <input type="checkbox"/> Access to basic tools and platforms for content creation and dissemination. <input type="checkbox"/> Some dedicated space and resources for hosting SciComm/PE events.	<input type="checkbox"/> Well-developed infrastructure to support full-fledged SciComm/PE activities <input type="checkbox"/> Access to advanced tools, technologies, and platforms to not only develop and disseminate content but also to analyse the metrics. <input type="checkbox"/> Dedicated space for SciComm/PE events and activities (like a Science Engagement Centre/Museum etc.).
Funding	<input type="checkbox"/> No funds allocated specifically for SciComm/PE to carry out regular tasks. <input type="checkbox"/> Difficulty securing external funding due to lack of clarity about the SciComm/PE function.	<input type="checkbox"/> Moderate allocation of institutional funding for SciComm/PE to carry out regular tasks. <input type="checkbox"/> Funding for new SciComm/PE programmes not easily available. <input type="checkbox"/> Ability to raise <u>some</u> external funding.	<input type="checkbox"/> Funding for SciComm/PE is readily available to carry out regular tasks and implement new programmes. <input type="checkbox"/> External funding is easily attainable, as SciComm/PE are fundamental to institutional vision.
Professional Development	<input type="checkbox"/> No clarity on career pathways for SciComm/PE team members - enabling promotions, increased responsibilities, and leadership roles. <input type="checkbox"/> No clarity on the qualifications, skills, and experiences needed for progression. <input type="checkbox"/> No institutional mechanisms or opportunities to ensure the SciComm/PE staff stays up-to-date on the latest trends in SciComm/PE.	<input type="checkbox"/> Moderate clarity on career pathways for SciComm/PE team members - enabling promotions, increased responsibilities, and leadership roles. <input type="checkbox"/> Some clarity on the qualifications, skills, and experiences needed for progression. <input type="checkbox"/> Occasional institutional mechanisms or opportunities to ensure the SciComm/PE staff stays up-to-date on the latest trends in SciComm/PE.	<input type="checkbox"/> Clear career pathways for SciComm/PE team members - enabling promotions, increased responsibilities, and leadership roles. <input type="checkbox"/> Adequate institutional mechanisms or opportunities to ensure the SciComm/PE staff stays up-to-date on the latest trends in SciComm/PE.
Collaboration	<input type="checkbox"/> No interaction between the SciComm/PE office and internal stakeholders such as scientific and non-scientific staff, students, and leadership. <input type="checkbox"/> No collaboration with external actors (institutions, individuals, media, NGOs, etc.) for SciComm/PE.	<input type="checkbox"/> Moderate interaction between the SciComm/PE office and internal stakeholders such as scientific and non-scientific staff, students, and leadership, with room for improvement. <input type="checkbox"/> Some collaboration with external actors (institutions, individuals, media, NGOs, etc.) for SciComm/PE.	<input type="checkbox"/> Well-established and institutionalised collaboration between SciComm/PE office and internal stakeholders such as scientific and non-scientific staff, students, and leadership. <input type="checkbox"/> Collaboration with external actors (institutions, individuals, media, NGOs, etc.) for SciComm/PE programmes.
Culture	<input type="checkbox"/> Very low or no awareness or understanding of the importance of SciComm/PE among institutional stakeholders.	<input type="checkbox"/> Growing awareness and integration of SciComm/PE into institutional culture.	<input type="checkbox"/> Full integration of SciComm/PE into institutional culture <input type="checkbox"/> Adequate opportunities for staff and students to

	<input type="checkbox"/> No opportunities for staff and students to participate in SciComm/PE activities. <input type="checkbox"/> No recognition of SciComm/PE efforts by SciComm team, staff and students. <input type="checkbox"/> No training in SciComm/PE for researchers, staff, and students to retain their interest, knowledge, and skills.	<input type="checkbox"/> Moderate opportunities for staff and students to participate in SciComm/PE activities. <input type="checkbox"/> Limited recognition of SciComm/PE efforts by SciComm team, staff and students <input type="checkbox"/> Limited to moderate training in SciComm/PE for researchers, staff, and students to retain their interest, knowledge, and skills.	participate in SciComm/PE activities. <input type="checkbox"/> Explicit, formal recognition of SciComm/PE efforts by SciComm team, staff and students <input type="checkbox"/> Regular training in SciComm/PE for researchers, staff, and students to retain their interests, knowledge, and skills.
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Glossary

Science Communication: The practice of conveying scientific information to diverse audiences in an accessible and understandable manner, fostering a bridge between the scientific community and the public.

Public Engagement: The active involvement of the public in scientific processes, discussions, or decision-making, promoting two-way communication and collaboration between scientists and non-expert audiences.

Institutional Mandate: The officially assigned responsibilities and objectives that guide an organisation or institution in its pursuit of specific activities.

Mission: A concise statement defining the fundamental purpose and goals of an organisation, emphasising its commitment to specific values and objectives.

Vision: A forward-looking statement outlining the desired future state or impact an organisation aims to achieve through its actions and initiatives.

Institutional culture: This is the mindset and daily behaviour inside an organisation that shapes how people value and practise SciComm/PE. It shows up in what leadership celebrates, what colleagues encourage, and what gets time, money, and recognition. When SciComm is part of the culture, researchers feel proud to engage with society, collaboration with communities feels natural, and communication isn't treated as an afterthought but as a shared responsibility.

SciComm/PE Strategy: A structured plan outlining the approach, methods, timelines, and monitoring and evaluation matrix for effective science communication or public engagement initiatives, tailored to specific goals and target audiences.

Infrastructure: This covers both physical and digital systems that make SciComm work possible and smooth. Think of the basics like a well-designed website, regular newsletters, social media channels, graphic and video production tools, event spaces, podcast or recording setups, and accessible platforms for sharing research with different communities.

Further resources for institutions to build capability for SciComm/PE

A detailed SciComm/PE checklist for institutions can be found here: [W Institutional SciComm/PE check-list.docx](#)

Find here a questionnaire that will help you map the goals, objectives, and implementation strategy of SciComm/PE function at your institution: [W Mapping Institutional Goals for SciComm/PE.docx](#)

If you're thinking about developing a Science Communication team at your institution, check out these [Frequently Asked Questions \(FAQs\) on Building Institutional Communication Functions](#)

Read the full SciComm ThinkLabs report [here](#).

This [Institutional SciComm Tool](#) is inspired by the EDGE tool by the NCCPE, UK.